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CIVIL LIABILITY OF THE DATA CONTROLLER FOR THE LEAKAGE OF EMPLOYEE DATA

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the civil liability of data controllers due to the leakage of employee data. This study had as its research question: what is the type of civil liability of the data controller due to the leakage of employee data and its consequences? Given this problem, the following general objective emerged: to identify the type of civil liability applied to controllers due to the leakage of employee data and its application consequences. The specific objectives are: to study the General Data Protection Law, in its general aspects; to understand the flow of data in the labor contractual phases; and to analyze the types of civil liability and their application consequences. The methodology used had, as regards its objective, an exploratory approach and the bibliographic research technique, as a way of supporting its theories and hypotheses. As the main result of the research, it is observed that the best path to be followed is the application of objective liability, since it gives rise to greater protection of the rights of employees. This thought is supported by the identification of the consequences of application, since subjective liability results in the protection of the controller and the weakening of the holder.

Keywords: Civil liability. Controller. Data leak. Sensitive data. Worker.

INTRODUCTION

The world is currently in the Fourth Industrial Revolution, as a result of the social disruptions caused by the use of digital technology, computers, networks and software. Therefore, one of the factors that differentiates the Fourth Industrial Revolution from others is the widespread use of technology, with easy access for anyone and everyone. In addition, other scholars also claim that the Fifth Industrial Revolution has already begun, as a result of the use of Artificial Intelligence by the global population.

Due to the Fourth Revolution and the use of new technologies, phenomena known as Big Data and Datafication have emerged, not only in relation to virtual data, but also in relation to physical data. The term Big Data refers to the massive collection and storage of personal information obtained, while Datafication refers to the collection of information from everything that exists, whether in a virtual or physical environment.

Thus, day after day, the quantity and volume of data handled and accessed has been growing throughout society, such as in employment relationships, in which employers have data such as: employment record, date of birth, affiliations, bank accounts, religious beliefs, medical exams, among others.

Thus, there was intense concern regarding personal data, leading to the creation of the General Data Protection Law (LGPD) in Brazil in 2018, inspired by European dictates on the protection of personal data. The purpose of this legislation, as set out in its art. 1, is to protect the fundamental rights of freedom and privacy, as well as to guarantee the free development of the natural person's personality.

The LGPD brought in its scope aspects related to the civil liability of data processing agents, one of which is the controller, as a result of leaks of personal and sensitive data, such as employee data, which demonstrates once again the protectionist nature present in the legislation.

Thus, the question arose: what is the type of civil liability of the data controller due to the leaking of employee data and its consequences? In view of this problem, the following general objective emerged: to identify the type of civil liability applied to controllers due to the leaking of employee data and its application consequences. The specific objectives are: to study the General Data Protection Law, in its general aspects; to understand the flow of data in the labor contractual phases; and to analyze the types of civil liability and their application consequences.

This article is justified by the thematic relevance and the high rate of fragility and leakage of workers' data, as exemplified by the study by Kaspersky (Você RH, 2022), an international cybersecurity and digital privacy company, which determined that 47% of organizations were unable to protect their employees' data in 2021. As a result, it is necessary to carry out studies, aiming at a doctrinal improvement on the matter, as well as an application of equity in judicial decisions.

Therefore, the article is subdivided into three topics, the first addressing the general aspects of the General Data Protection Law; the second, dealing with the flow of data in the labor contractual phases; the third analyzing the types of civil liability and their consequences of application due to the leaking of employee data; finally, the final considerations follow.

DEVELOPMENT

Actions such as taking photos, sending emails, and calling friends generate data and information that needs to be stored. From this perspective, individuals now have very little control over the exposure of their private lives. As a result of the weakening of data control and the "increase in incidents related to data leaks" (Pinheiro, 2023, p. XIV), debates began on data protection and the prevention of new leaks in the European Union, leading to the enactment of the General Data Protection Regulation in 2016.

Brazil, following the European trend, enacted Law 13,709/2018 in 2018, which was promulgated by the President of the Republic, Michel Temer. Understanding the formation, at this point, it is necessary to study the objectives present in the Brazilian General Data Protection Law.

General aspects of the General Data Protection Law

The General Data Protection Law aims, as set out in its art. 1: “to protect the fundamental rights of freedom and privacy and the free development of the natural person's personality”. According to Cots and Oliveira (2021, p. 15), “the verb to protect says a lot about how the legislator saw the data subject, that is, in an unequal position in relation to those responsible for processing such data, making their vulnerability clear”. Applying the consumerist view of protection.

According to Pinheiro (2023), the focus on protecting the fundamental rights of privacy, freedom and the free development of the natural person proves its protective nature. In other words, the LGPD aims to guarantee the principle of transparency and security of the data collected, safeguarding the fundamental rights inherent to privacy, freedom of the citizen, development and free formation of the personality of each individual. Therefore, the LGPD's desire to protect the data subject from possible harm is clear, following the foundations inherent to the Law itself.

Regarding data types, Law 13.709/2018 includes different types, such as: personal, sensitive and anonymized. Personal data is defined in art. 5, I, as all “information related to an identified or identifiable natural person”. Therefore, the concept of personal data is broad, encompassing any information capable of identifying a person.

Article 5, item II of the LGPD states that sensitive data are personal data “about racial or ethnic origin, religious beliefs, political opinions, membership of a trade union or organization of a religious, philosophical or

political nature, data relating to health or sexual life, genetic or biomedical data, when linked to a natural person”. Therefore, this type of data forms an exhaustive list.

When it comes to data processing, the LGPD addresses in its first article, including the processing activity in both digital and physical media, by a natural or legal person under private or public law, aiming at the protection of the fundamental rights of freedom, privacy and the free development of the personality of the human person. According to art. 5°, X of the General Data Protection Law:

Art. 5°, X: processing: any operation carried out with personal data, such as those relating to collection, production, reception, classification, use, access, reproduction, transmission, distribution, processing, archiving, storage, elimination, evaluation or control of information, modification, communication, transfer, dissemination or extraction.

Based on the reading of the paragraph, it can be observed that the processing encompasses the data from its collection to its elimination. In accordance with Maldonado and Blum (2022), the finding of the scope of the processing is of great relevance, since the processing agent must keep all records of the operations carried out.

Furthermore, “the hypotheses are not cumulative, that is, a single activity on the list is already included in the concept of processing, no matter how simple it may be” (Cots; Oliveira, 2021, p.72). At this point, we delve into the subjects involved in the processing of personal data, in line with the Brazilian LGPD.

Furthermore, the LGPD encompasses four distinct subjects related to Brazilian data protection, namely: holder, controller, operator and manager. However, for the purposes of this article, comments will only be made on two subjects, namely: holder and controller.

Article 5, V, states that the data subject is any “natural person to whom the data that are the object of processing belong”. Therefore, it can be said that it is any natural person, physical person, identified or identifiable to whom the data refers.

In section VI of art. 5 of the LGPD, the controller is qualified as: “a natural or legal person, under public or private law, responsible for decisions regarding the processing of personal data”. According to Maldonado and Blum (2022), the controller has the greatest legal weight provided for in the LGPD, since he is responsible for making decisions related to the processing of personal data.

Finally, it is worth noting that among the four subjects present in the legislation, only two of them are on the exhaustive list of processing agents, namely the controller and the operator, on whom civil liability applies.

Data flow in the labor contract phases

After understanding the role of the subjects, it is clear that within the Labor Law relations, employees appear in the role of data subjects, while employers are in the position of controller.

Knowing the existence of weaknesses that many labor relations already have, there is a need to understand the impact and repercussions of the LGPD on employment contracts, since they encompass three phases: pre-contractual, contractual and post-contractual.

First of all, it is important to highlight that, in the pre-contractual phase, there is still no relationship between employee and employer, but rather only job offers or a selection process and an intention of the candidates to fill the vacancies. The Consolidation of Labor Laws (CLT) does not specifically provide for the pre-contractual phase, therefore, each employer may choose to regulate the hiring method, as long as it respects and protects the basic principles of data protection.

At this stage, the personal data requested should only be those necessary for the selection process, with subsequent review for recruitment purposes, ensuring the consent of the holder and finally, deleting the data, after the candidate is dismissed from the vacancy. However, if you choose to keep the candidate's data in a

database, he/she must be informed of the action, including the time it will be available (Pinheiro; Bomfim, 2020).

According to Araújo and Calcini (2020), in the pre-contractual phase, the collection of data that may in the future generate some discriminatory character among employees is expressly prohibited, for example: pregnancy tests.

It is known that during the pre-contractual phase, employers have access to resumes, functional and educational histories, address, marital status, among other data, which will consequently result in greater review and care on the part of human resources, not only in relation to the selection process, but also to the storage of all the data that they have obtained knowledge of.

Of course, the company cannot control the information contained in the resumes that are sent by candidates or those interested in a possible future vacancy. However, when the company receives these resumes for immediate use or for future selection processes, it is important that it pays attention to the use, transfer, storage and elimination of the personal and sensitive data contained therein (Molina, 2021).

Therefore, even in the pre-contractual phase, employers must be careful and take the necessary precautions, in order not to disregard any provision of the LGPD and incur civil liability for their act.

In the second phase, called contractual, there is a link between the employee and the employer, as well as a greater collection of documentation and personal data in order to regulate the hiring. Thus, it is understood that it is authorized, therefore, that consent does not need to be an autonomous contractual instrument, but rather a clause of the employment contract or an annex to it (Araújo; Calcini, 2020).

From this moment on, employers must carry out constant risk analysis and the need to adapt to the LGPD, carrying out training with departments, reviewing contractual clauses and

policies.

Another factor that deserves to be highlighted is related to the processing of sensitive personal data, such as: health, race, biometrics, among others. Since, although there are legal grounds for collecting certain sensitive data, these data require greater protection from the controller-employer.

An example is health-related data, since it is necessary to analyze or review the contract signed with the medical service provider in order to guarantee the protection of sensitive data, as well as to protect against possible liability for security incidents.

Another common practice among employers is the collection of biometric data, whether for entry into security departments or for timekeeping. However, the collection of biometric data is also included in the list of sensitive data, and therefore, each employer must take all appropriate processing measures regarding the data provided by employees.

The third phase (post-contractual) corresponds to the employee's termination of the existing relationship, and may reach this phase for various reasons, such as: death, dismissal for just cause, dismissal for just cause, closure of the establishment, among others.

According to Alcântara (2021), at the end of the employment contract, there is data that is relevant and sensitive to the holder, and may have varied content, such as: reason for termination of the employment contract, severance pay, if the employee died, it will contain information about death and related information, data for future reference to the new employer.

At this stage, there is a need to comply with the principle of transparency, informing the employee that the use of the data will be terminated by legal determination or at the request of the employee-owner. It is worth noting that, with regard to the request of the employee-owner, it is relativized in labor relations, given that there are legal provisions that require the storage of employee documents and data.

During storage, employers must follow the respective guidelines for data processing, including carrying out anonymization techniques, as well as carrying out the correct and mandatory disposal after the legal storage period (Araújo ; Calcini, 2020), mainly due to the serious consequences resulting from non-compliance with the provisions of the LGPD.

Species and consequences application of objective or subjective liability relating to the leaking of employee data

This theme generates many doctrinal divergences, however, following the line of the doctrinaires Diniz, Stolze and Pamplona Filho, three assumptions can be listed, such as: human conduct, damage or loss and causal link.

Human conduct is the master expression of human will, and may arise from an action or omission, and this is a necessary premise for the formation of civil liability (Stolze; Pamplona Filho, 2024). In the positive case, the agent voluntarily practices that conduct and in the negative case, the person who caused the damage voluntarily failed to observe his duty to act.

With regard to damage, it can be defined as the reduction of a legal asset, of any nature, causing injury, whether in the patrimonial or moral sphere (Cavaliere Filho, 2023).

The last general assumption of liability according to the tripartite theory is the causal link between the damage and the action. In the words of Diniz (2024, p. 48): “the link between the loss and the action is called a “causal link”, so that the harmful event must originate from the action, directly or as its foreseeable consequence”. It can be seen, therefore, that in order to generate civil liability, it is not enough for the action and the damage to occur, but they must be connected to each other in order to obtain compensation.

When it comes to types of civil liability, the second major part of the doctrine, it is subdivided into two: subjective and objective.

Subjective liability based on fault and objective liability arising from the law.

liability is that which arises from the negligent or intentional act of the agent and requires proof from the victim for the obligation to compensate to fall. The conduct occurs through negligence, recklessness, incompetence or intent according to the majority understanding of the doctrine (Diniz, 2024).

Returning to the assumptions discussed in the previous topic, in subjective liability all elements must be proven: conduct, damage and causal link. From this perspective, Stolze and Pamplona Filho (2024) comment that since it is a fact constituting the law, the burden of proving the defendant's guilt in the broad sense falls on the plaintiff.

It is worth noting that the notion of guilt still raises great questions today, given that if the victim does not prove the agent's guilt, compensation will not occur, according to this type of liability. Therefore, it was necessary to change the meaning of guilt, thus giving rise to the objective theory/type of civil liability.

Civil liability, in turn, also known as risk theory, arose due to society's need to expand the meaning of guilt. This theory is based on the exercise of an activity, therefore, whoever exercises it must answer for the damages they cause (Diniz, 2024).

In this regard, Stolze and Pamplona Filho (2024, p. 18) state:

However, there are cases in which it is not even necessary to establish fault. In these cases, we are faced with what is conventionally called "objective civil liability". According to this type of liability, the intent or fault in the conduct of the agent causing the damage is legally irrelevant, given that only the existence of a causal link between the damage and the conduct of the responsible agent is necessary for the duty to compensate to arise.

That said, fault or intent still exists, but it will not be necessary to prove it to generate compensation, given the legislation or the risk of the activity itself. Therefore, it can be stated that objective civil liability arises from two sources: the law and the theory of risk.

The consequences of applying objective and subjective liability for the controller are provided for in Section III of Chapter VI of the LGPD, "making clear the possibility of repairing patrimonial, moral, individual or collective damages, whenever these result from a violation of personal data protection legislation" (Maldonado; Blum, 2022, p. RL-1.13).

It turns out that, in the area of civil liability presented in the LGPD, there are great doctrinal debates about the type to be followed, given that it is not precisely clear as to the application of objective or subjective liability. Unlike the Consumer Defense Code, which is explicit in adopting objective liability, the LGPD did not follow the same path of explicitness; however, when carrying out a systematic interpretation, one comes to the conclusion of the application of subjective liability (Maldonado; Blum, 2022).

It is worth noting that one of the fundamental aspects of the defense of this doctrinal aspect concerns the large set of duties established for the controller in the processing of data and, if not respected, they are subject to civil liability. Therefore, it can be observed as a consequence of the application of the subjective responsibility of the controller, that it is necessary to prove the culpable attitude, whether due to the violation of the LGPD or due to failure to take adequate security measures for data processing (Maldonado; Blum, 2022).

It turns out that the application of this type of civil liability in labor relations may lead to an even greater weakening, given that the employee is already in a vulnerable position (Camino, 2004). Therefore, placing yet another burden on the employee so that he or she may seek legal protection is very onerous.

However, the application of subjective liability to the controller provides protection for the controller, since there would be no point in creating duties to be followed in the LGPD, if at a time of accountability, the analysis of compliance with duties was not taken into consideration (Guedes and Meireles, 2023),

since according to the subjective theory, it is not possible to hold someone responsible for the damage suffered, if there is no culpable or willful conduct (Stolze; Pamplona Filho, 2024).

The doctrinal line that supports objective liability in the LGPD argues that although the article does not precisely indicate the liability of the controller and the operator, it does not demonstrate that there is any doubt that it deals with objective liability (Colombo; Facchini, 2018). Due to the objective of the LGPD and its protectionist nature, in comparison with the harmful potential of data processing, the use of the objective line proves to be the safest means for the holders-employees.

Another point that deserves to be highlighted concerns the widespread use of objective civil liability in the labor field, such as work accidents, abuse of the employer's management power and acts of employees or agents (Bertotti, 2014). Therefore, since there is already widespread use of this type, classifying the controller as liable in cases of employee leaks would be the most logical and assertive path to follow.

As a consequence of applying the controller's objective liability, it would be easier for the employee-holders to hold the company accountable, since the element of fault would not need to be proven, providing greater protection (Maldonado; Blum, 2022). However, for the controller, the application of objective liability could weaken labor relations, since it would lead to a greater number of lawsuits due to the leaking of employee data, increasing the costs of defenses and proof of compliance with all legal duties.

In addition to complying with the LGPD, employer-controllers must also follow the dictates of labor laws, the Constitution and regulatory standards. Thus, the subjective application of liability provides a greater framework for protection and supervisory oversight.

CONCLUSION

This article asked the following question: what is the type of civil liability of the data controller due to the leaking of employee data and its consequences? Therefore, this scientific article presents as a result of the aforementioned problem that the LGPD provided for the possibility of applying civil liability to data processing agents, thus encompassing the figure of the controller. However, this legislation did not clearly state its legal position regarding the type to be applied, allowing doctrinaires and jurists to interpret and apply the rule.

In the labor sphere, the employee finds himself in a vulnerable position vis-à-vis the employer (controller), due to the very configuration of the employment contract. In addition, the employee has access to various personal and sensitive data in his/her employment contract, such as medical exams, biometrics, health history, address, affiliations, religious opinion, etc.

Therefore, being unable to refuse to provide the data, if he wishes to continue in an employment relationship, the employee-holder once again places himself in a vulnerable position, seeking from the employer-controller the reliability of the processing of his personal and sensitive data.

However, when, due to a leak of data belonging to the employee-holders, they seek legal protection, they are surrounded by legal instability regarding the type of civil liability applied to their case. This is one of the reasons for defending objective liability, in order to not make it even more onerous for the employee-holder to assert his/her right before the Court, since, if it is proven that the leak occurred and that damage resulted from it, it would not be necessary to prove the fault of the employer-controller.

Another point defended by the minority group concerns the systematic analysis of the LGPD, in which one can see the legislator's concern in protecting the holders of personal data throughout its structure, bringing concepts of treatment, subjects involved, etc., a vision

similar to that of the Consumer Defense Code.

On the other hand, following the majority view, the LGPD follows the general Brazilian rule of application of subjective liability, giving the employee-holder the burden of proving the existence of the three elements of civil liability: conduct, damage and causal link. According to the current view, it would not make sense for the LGPD to stipulate guidelines for the processing of data by the controller, if in the factual case, it was not taken into account whether or not the guidelines were followed.

In the face of subjective liability, the highly protective nature of the employee-owners is weakened and reversed, in the case of civil liability, since the controlling employer becomes more protected, in terms of the need to prove his/her guilt, in a broad sense.

Thus, when dealing with employment relationships, the best path to follow is the application of objective liability, since it provides greater protection and makes it easier for employees to obtain rights, since they are already in an unequal position with their employers. This thought is supported by the identification of the consequences of application, since, as previously mentioned, subjective liability results in the protection of the controller and the weakening of the data subject. In contrast, objective liability reverses the poles, allowing greater protection for the data subject and weakening, but also an incentive to ensure the correct processing of data by the controller.

This time, the thematic relevance for students and legal professionals, and for employees and employers, is noted, given that it is of utmost importance to understand and adapt to the recent and growing legal branch, which permeates and brings great repercussions in the labor and civil spheres.

Finally, it is recommended that the application of civil liability in cases of employee data leaks be reviewed in the labor-civil sphere, in order to unify the application of objective liability, which is already applied in several other labor disputes, such as workplace

accidents and abuse of managerial power. Using the dualistic system, in which, even if there is no express provision in the text of the law, objective liability is applied, such as the civil liability provided for in art. 936 of the Civil Code, since the fact itself is so beneficial that it goes beyond the barriers of theories of risk, activity and even the analysis of fault.

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